

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) FIS_BZFP

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: FIS_BZFP

Bond precision: C-C = 0.0038 Å

Wavelength=1.54184

Cell: a=10.9381(9) b=12.9028(10) c=13.3228(12)
 alpha=109.883(9) beta=109.949(9) gamma=97.278(9)
Temperature: 293 K

	Calculated	Reported
Volume	1598.2(3)	1598.2(3)
Space group	P -1	P -1
Hall group	-P 1	-P 1
Moiety formula	C15 H10 O6, 2(C13 H9 N O)	C15 H10 O6, 2(C13 H9 N O)
Sum formula	C41 H28 N2 O8	C41 H28 N2 O8
Mr	676.65	676.65
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.406	1.406
Z	2	2
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	0.811	0.811
F000	704.0	704.0
F000'	706.30	
h, k, lmax	13, 16, 16	13, 16, 16
Nref	6658	6470
Tmin, Tmax	0.816, 0.885	0.735, 1.000
Tmin'	0.816	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.735 Tmax=1.000
AbsCorr = MULTI-SCAN

Data completeness= 0.972

Theta(max)= 75.847

R(reflections)= 0.0512(5008)

wR2(reflections)=
0.1517(6470)

S = 1.032

Npar= 460

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

Alert level B

PLAT230_ALERT_2_B Hirshfeld Test Diff for C16 --C17 . 8.0 s.u.

Alert level C

PLAT230_ALERT_2_C Hirshfeld Test Diff for O11A --C12A . 5.1 s.u.
PLAT250_ALERT_2_C Large U3/U1 Ratio for <U(i,j)> Tensor(Resd 1) 2.2 Note
PLAT355_ALERT_3_C Long O-H (X0.82,N0.98A) O3P - H3OP . 1.01 Ang.
PLAT906_ALERT_3_C Large K Value in the Analysis of Variance 5.954 Check
PLAT911_ALERT_3_C Missing FCF Refl Between Thmin & STh/L= 0.600 8 Report
1 0 4, 2 2 8, -5 -7 12, -8 1 14, -7 -2 15, -7 -1 15,
-6 -1 15, -6 0 15,

Alert level G

PLAT007_ALERT_5_G Number of Unrefined Donor-H Atoms 4 Report
H3OP H4OP H3O H7O
PLAT154_ALERT_1_G The s.u.'s on the Cell Angles are Equal ..(Note) 0.009 Degree
PLAT199_ALERT_1_G Reported _cell_measurement_temperature (K) 293 Check
PLAT200_ALERT_1_G Reported _diffrn_ambient_temperature (K) 293 Check
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O11 . 105.5 Degree
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O11A . 105.5 Degree
PLAT480_ALERT_4_G Long H...A H-Bond Reported H18 ..O11A . 2.65 Ang.
PLAT720_ALERT_4_G Number of Unusual/Non-Standard Labels 2 Note
H3OP H4OP
PLAT899_ALERT_4_G SHELXL2018 is Outdated and Succeeded by SHELXL 2019/3 Note
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L= 0.600 180 Note
PLAT933_ALERT_2_G Number of HKL-OMIT Records in Embedded .res File 8 Note
-7 -2 15, -7 -1 15, -6 0 15, -6 -3 16, -5 -1 16, -5 -7 12,
-6 -1 15, -6 -2 16,
PLAT941_ALERT_3_G Average HKL Measurement Multiplicity 1.8 Low
PLAT969_ALERT_5_G The 'Henn et al.' R-Factor-gap value 3.293 Note
Predicted wR2: Based on SigI**2 4.61 or SHELX Weight 14.71 Note
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density. 9 Info

- 0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
1 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
5 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
14 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

3 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data

7 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
4 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
4 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
2 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

PLATON version of 23/04/2026; check.def file version of 30/03/2026

duplicate check

No duplication found
